

SUSTAINABILITY SURPRISES:

DO INVESTORS REACT TO

ESG NEWS?

Güler ARAS¹

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9438-719>

Sunay ÇIRALI²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5906-1989>

Abstract

This study investigates the effect of news about environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues on investor behavior, focusing on abnormal stock returns. The study conducts an empirical analysis of a comprehensive dataset of 3,448 ESG news events involving companies listed in major stock indices in Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) nations between January 1, 2022, and December 31, 2023. The paper uses an event study methodology within the CAPM framework to calculate cumulative abnormal returns around announcement dates. The findings show that ESG news produces statistically significant abnormal returns within a narrow event window [-1, +1]. This suggests that investors immediately integrate sustainability-related information into company prices. However, this effect decreases in wider windows [-3, +3], showing that market reactions are temporary. Additional analysis demonstrates that the intensity of market reactions is not significantly different between positive and negative ESG news. This suggests that investors focus on the content and impact of ESG disclosures rather than their trend. In conclusion, the study provides empirical evidence that ESG news delivers short-term economic value to capital markets and significantly impacts investor behavior. The study contributes to the literature by offering a dynamic perspective on the processing and use of sustainability information in global financial markets.

¹ Prof., Dr., Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi, İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi, Öğretim Üyesi, dr.guler.aras@gmail.com

²Doktora Öğrencisi, Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü; Ar. Gör., Doğu Üniversitesi, İktisadi İdari ve Sosyal Bilimler Fakültesi, İşletme Bölümü, scirali@dogus.edu.tr

Keywords: ESG Investments, Event Study, Stock Market Reaction, CAPM, Sustainability News, Investor Sentiment.

INTRODUCTION

This study investigates whether ESG news generates short-term abnormal stock returns. Numerous studies examine the relationship between ESG performance and firm value, focusing on long-term performance, risk exposure, or capital costs. Nonetheless, research analyzing investor responses to ESG-related news using real-time data remains limited. Companies' ESG disclosures are voluntary, vary widely, and are less standardized than conventional financial data, creating uncertainty about their value and market relevance. Short-term abnormal returns analysis is a behavior-based technique for assessing the impact of ESG-related news on investor perceptions and its fast integration into capital markets. This technique enables an evaluation of both the normative or reputational value of ESG information and its short-term economic value.

We develop a reference asset-pricing model using stock returns around the public release dates of ESG news, identify abnormal and cumulative abnormal returns, and analyze these cumulative abnormal returns using the event-study methodology. The existence and statistical significance of short-term abnormal returns serve as quantitative evidence that ESG-related information is incorporated into investors' decision-making and reflected in market prices. The research problem is operationalized using observable financial data and assessed using econometric methods.

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The primary objective of this paper is to investigate whether news related to ESG affects investors' perceptions, thereby leading to abnormal short-term stock returns. We attempt to identify the existence, direction, and statistical significance of abnormal and cumulative abnormal returns associated with ESG news items. The main question that the analysis in this study addresses is:

“Does information related to ESG influence investor preferences, resulting in short-term abnormal stock performance?”

The empirical analysis investigating this research question uses multiple news articles

addressing sustainability concerns across firms in different nations. Corresponding to the study problem and question, we initially articulate the following hypothesis:

H1: News releases related to ESG generate statistically significant abnormal stock returns.

To investigate the temporal duration of this impact, our subsequent sub-hypothesis is formulated:

H1a: The impact of abnormal stock returns associated with the release of ESG-related news diminishes as the event window increases and eventually becomes statistically insignificant.

To investigate whether the effect differs based on the sentiment of the news, we formulate subsequent sub-hypotheses:

H1b: Stock returns influenced by ESG-related news exhibit statistically significant variations based on the sentiment of the news (positive or negative).

We methodically examine these hypotheses using an event-study methodology, providing empirical insights into the short-term price implications of ESG-related information and the temporal dynamics that influence investor reactions in capital markets.

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Corporate sustainability has been viewed as a non-financial, purely ethical issue, but has become a key element in decision-making about individuals' finances.

Recent corporate scandals, environmental disasters, and systemic financial disruptions indicate that a narrow definition of pure financial valuation is inappropriate, and that non-financial information (sustainability-related) is also paramount in explaining firm value.

Corporate sustainability refers to a company's ability to achieve long-term profitability by integrating effective business practices, governance, social responsibility, and environmental awareness (Elkington 2004; Bansal 2005). This integrated strategy rejects the shareholder-centric approach and emphasizes the importance of broad stakeholder

participation in achieving financial benefits. ESG information has become increasingly significant in the capital markets. This is because sustainability issues affect existing and emerging rules, consumer preferences, and investor behavior.

When new information emerges about a company, it may prompt investors, economists, and other market participants to reassess their views on its cash flow and risk profile. In this regard, ESG news and announcements can change how investors perceive and price assets by creating information disruptions.

The primary concepts on the subject are the “*Social Impact Hypothesis*” and the “*Shift of Focus Hypothesis*.”

The Social Impact Hypothesis states that better ESG performance may increase company value by promoting stakeholder relationships, reducing conflict costs, and improving corporate reputation (Donaldson and Preston 1995; Friede et al. 2015; Preston and O’Bannon 1997; Servaes and Tamayo 2013; Waddock and Graves 1997). The theory suggests that firms that manage environmental and social problems achieve higher levels of consumer satisfaction and employee engagement, gain greater access to capital, and face fewer adverse legal repercussions. From this perspective, ESG activities are seen not only as ethical obligations but also as strategic investments that deliver long-term benefits. Empirical studies support this idea, indicating that firms with superior ESG performance typically have lower capital costs (El Ghoual et al. 2011; Goss and Roberts 2011), lower risk (Albuquerque et al. 2019), and greater resilience during periods of market volatility (Lins et al. 2017). Sustainability policies can serve as a risk-management strategy, protecting enterprises from adverse shocks and increasing their long-term value.

According to the Shift of Focus Hypothesis, ESG practices can divert managerial attention and the company’s financial resources away from profit-maximizing expenditures (Becchetti et al. 2012; Friedman 1970). This view holds that organizations’ efforts to maintain sustainability may entail costs rather than financial rewards, thereby reducing stakeholder value. If investors perceive corporations’ ESG initiatives as superficial or insincere, sustainability information may have a negligible positive impact on the market or may be subject to investor penalties. Moreover, a contradiction exists

between these theoretical frameworks, and the empirical evidence in the ESG performance literature is uncertain. As a result, it focuses on the importance of examining investors' rapid reactions to sustainability-related information.

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) is an underlying framework for analyzing asset prices as a function of new information about the market. The semi-strong form of the Efficient Market Hypothesis posits that stock prices incorporate all publicly available information rapidly and accurately (Fama 1970).

From an EMH perspective, if investors value sustainability information, the stock price should reflect this when it becomes public. EMH also notes that any abnormal price changes could be temporary. Hence, after new information has been absorbed, price movement corresponds to the arrival of a new event on the market, not to its occurrence. This assumption is crucial for short-term event studies, which assume that abnormal returns are observed at the time of release and then decline over time. The literature on ESG news almost uniformly supports this view. Research has shown that the most abnormal returns occur in relatively narrow event windows, after which rapid price changes typically occur (Serafeim and Yoon 2022; Vu et al. 2024).

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EMH investigates how investors in the market process information, while behavioral finance considers how irrational investors respond to information. Behavioral finance theories, for example, argue that investors are prone to cognitive biases, limited attention, and emotional reactions, leading to transient mispricing following the receipt of an announcement (Barberis et al. 1998; Shiller 1981). Attention-related effects are particularly pronounced for prices affected by ESG news. This can cause investors to overvalue ESG information and, thus, react to it exuberantly. The Overreaction Hypothesis posits that investors may initially overreact to information, causing prices to diverge from their intrinsic value, and that a correction is expected to follow soon thereafter (De Bondt and Thaler 1985). From this perspective, ESG news triggers very short-term reactions, leading to attention-seeking trading rather than systematic mispricing. In such cases, abnormal returns decrease as trade volume stabilizes, leading

to temporary data shocks rather than long-term consequences.

In summary, EMH and the Overreaction Hypothesis provide theoretical frameworks that yield similar results regarding investor reactions to ESG news, despite differing methodologies. Because information in the EMH can be quickly and fully incorporated into prices after it is made public, if ESG news helps support firm value, it can be rapidly incorporated into prices through rational investor pricing. Each abnormal return is temporary. Within this view, rapid price movements are considered an example of market efficiency (Fama 1970). On the contrary, behavioral finance explains short-term pricing patterns by accounting for psychological factors such as limited investor attention, emotional reactivity, and the engaging nature of news events. This perspective holds that because ESG news is prominent, investors will temporarily pay attention to it, regardless of its impact on underlying value, leading to short-term price changes (Barberis et al. 1998; Shiller 1981).

The event analysis method is valuable for providing researchers with a basis for assessing news events in the market. Event studies measure abnormal returns on the event date by comparing actual stock returns with a predicted return generated by an asset pricing model (MacKinlay 1997). Short-term event studies are particularly appropriate for ESG news for several reasons. This strategy also limits the impact of extraneous information and macroeconomic fluctuations.

This method computes CARs across multiple event panels to estimate the volume and duration of market reactions. Event windows $[-1, +1]$ are at the narrowest end, highlighting the near-term response, while larger windows $[-3, +3]$ indicate whether the impacts persist over time. To this end, event study methods relevant to ESG-oriented news, as noted, objectively assess the effectiveness of sustainability information in influencing investors' decision-making and determine how this action translates into actual financial impact.

The event study method assumes that the EMH will incorporate new data into asset prices immediately. Fama et al. (1969) introduced the theoretical and empirical foundations of this methodology. The authors define abnormal returns systematically as the difference between the expected and actual returns around events that influence a company's value. MacKinlay (1997) introduces the current event study methodology. This technique for event studies has five primary components: (1) *event definition*, (2) *estimation window*, (3) *event window*, (4) *abnormal return model*, and (5) *statistical testing procedures*. Our research utilizes the conventional event study methodology, utilizing a CAPM model to calculate abnormal returns. We chose narrow event windows for these analyses to minimize the effects of information leakage and simultaneous shocks.

In recent years, event studies using daily data have attracted attention in the literature. Brown and Warner (1985) demonstrate that simple models can generate strong and accurate results in many situations by employing daily returns in their event studies. But on event days, more volatility and distributional variance can distort standard test statistics. So, these circumstances require methodological caution when interpreting event research results. Boehmer et al. (1991) also note that standard tests often ignore changes in variance on event days. The authors propose a methodological solution by developing a standardized cross-sectional testing framework. In the same way, Corrado (1989) emphasizes the importance of non-parametric testing when assumptions about distributions are ignored. Corrado's rank-based approach suggests that nonparametric tests are more effective for non-normally distributed samples or datasets with outliers. Therefore, numerous recent articles in WoS and Scopus employ the Corrado rank test with parametric tests.

Another methodological problem in event studies arises from the clustering of event data across companies. This creates a cross-sectional correlation. This issue is significant for events that affect the entire market, including regulatory adjustments, macroeconomic disruptions, geopolitical incidents, and environmental regulations. In this context, Kolari and Pynnönen (2010) make a significant contribution by analyzing adjusted test statistics

that account for cross-sectional correlation. Patell (1976) illustrated that event studies are an effective tool in the accounting literature by analyzing market responses to the announcement of revenue forecasts. In subsequent years, this methodology has been used for various corporate events, including mergers and acquisitions, credit rating adjustments, and bankruptcy announcements.

The event study literature has made significant advancements in both methodology and practicality thus far. The present research suggests that employing short event windows and reporting sensitivity tests with alternative test statistics are crucial for the reliability of event study results. The event research design utilized in this paper generally complies with the existing classical event study literature. The choice of short event windows, [-1, +1] and [-3, +3], along with a 255-day estimation window (The 255 day estimation window was selected because it approximately represents one year of trading day), aligns with conventional methods for minimizing information leakage and parallel-shock effects. Moreover, using market risk-free interest rates in the market model to estimate abnormal returns yields consistent expected return estimates across a multinational sample. The study's approach employs nonparametric tests (Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis) to account for deviations in the observed distributions on event days and to address increased variance. The implementation of IQR for outlier removal and the formulation of a "materiality" metric based on the absolute values of both pre- and post-event CAR differences enhance methodological robustness and aid in assessing the significance of ESG news from a market perspective.

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News-based event studies differ from typical sustainability investment evaluations. Compared with traditional studies, these investigations focus on real-time news coverage of the corporation rather than the organization's announcements. Serafeim and Yoon (2022) published an important study that was conducted with this idea. In their event study using ESG news from the TruValue Labs database, the authors demonstrate that market participants exhibit considerable reactions to ESG issues, with responses varying by news sentiment, visibility, and content. The research confirms the notion that the informative content of ESG news is heterogeneous, suggesting that abnormal returns

(AR/CAR) during the event window are associated with news characteristics. Li et al. (2024) indicate that retail investors adjust their investment decisions in response to ESG news, especially when they believe it will have a significant impact on firm performance. The study shows that ESG news affects both the prices and the types of investors. Dorfleitner et al. (2024) utilize natural language processing (NLP) sentiment analysis to evaluate ESG news content, demonstrating that the average abnormal returns of positive and negative ESG news on the event day exhibit large disparities in both sentiment and importance.

Vu et al. (2024), on the other hand, indicate that reactions are usually temporary. Authors demonstrate, with a news-based portfolio analysis, that the market's reaction to ESG news is frequently temporary and may even reverse in some periods of time and conditions, indicating that such reactions do not consistently produce a long-term premium.

Lee et al. (2015) state that voluntary carbon disclosure is related to negative abnormal stock returns. This means that investors perceive voluntary carbon disclosure as a signal that environmental regulations and climate change will impose future costs.

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The literature analyzing the influence of ESG implementation on stock returns encompasses research that evaluates both positive and negative ESG information using long-term pricing models. These studies investigate whether investors exhibit a greater response to negative ESG information, specifically assessing the presence of a pricing bias.

Numerous studies in the literature demonstrate that negative ESG information has a greater and more enduring impact on stock returns. Bolton and Kacperczyk (2021) argue, in a panel data study on carbon emissions and environmental harms, that corporations with poor environmental performance offer higher expected returns and that investors assign these companies an environmental risk premium. This outcome suggests that investors consistently penalize companies for negative environmental information. Pankratz et al. (2023) similarly examines the effects of negative climate change news on corporate value, demonstrating a significant decrease in the value of companies perceived

as environmentally sensitive. These findings support the ESG literature's view that "negative news" exerts greater influence on the price structure.

The literature generally investigates the long-term effects of negative events, such as ESG inconsistencies and scandals, on stock performance. Aouadi and Marsat (2018) suggest that inconsistencies in corporate social responsibility (CSR) diminish corporate value, but the influence of positive CSR initiatives on stock performance is comparatively minimal. This information asymmetry arises from the perception that investors are more responsive to negative signals concerning reputational damage and legal liabilities. Nonetheless, various studies in the literature indicate that there is no significant asymmetry in the influence of positive and negative news on CSR. Friede et al. (2015) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis demonstrating that the correlation between CSR achievement and financial performance is predominantly positive or neutral; however, this correlation does not result in a consistent asymmetry in differentiating between positive and negative information. The authors conclude that CSR information has become a mandatory consideration for investors, thereby reducing the impact of news on pricing. Albuquerque et al. (2020) similarly indicate that companies exhibiting strong ESG performance excelled during crises. Nevertheless, the study found no evidence that positive ESG news produced greater abnormal returns relative to market performance during regular periods. This research shows that ESG information serves as a protective function and that positive news does not consistently confer an advantage.

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Research that does not identify an asymmetry in the positive-negative news mostly argues that ESG information is incrementally incorporated into long-term prices. Hong et al. (2012) suggest that the influence of portfolio-level environmental and social responsibility dimensions on equity returns is shaped by long-term investor preferences rather than momentary shocks, based on their analysis of the underlying determinants. This conclusion is predicated on the belief that the ESG profile's consistency outweighs its informational component.

Research demonstrating that negative ESG news generates more pronounced market reactions has mainly focused on unforeseen, major environmental catastrophes, scandals, and regulatory challenges. On the other hand, panel data and portfolio-based statistics

show that ESG information reacts to prices more slowly and in smaller stages. This suggests that the quality and consistency of information in a market are more important than the effect of news.

In summary, the literature encompasses numerous studies examining the impact of ESG information on financial performance. Nonetheless, this research primarily examines ESG ratings and profitability indicators. Research involving real-time and short-term analyses is notably scarce. Moreover, this prevailing research primarily focuses on US companies and specific ESG dimensions. We intend to address this deficiency in the literature through a multinational, multidimensional event study.

The data set for our analysis includes the following:

- *Country*: Selected OECD countries,
- *Market Return*: Return of the selected stock market index in the relevant country,
- *Risk-Free Interest Rate*: Yield of 10-year government bonds in the relevant country,
- *Stock Return*: Daily return of the company that is featured in the news,
- *Event Date*: Date the ESG news is published in the press.

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We examine 3,448 ESG-related news articles written between January 1, 2022, and December 31, 2023, about companies listed in selected stock market indices of OECD nations. The ESG news used in the study was obtained from the FactSet TruValue Labs database. The FactSet TruValue Labs database utilizes artificial intelligence to aggregate positive and negative ESG-related event data from over 200,000 sources daily. We examine investors' views of these companies using structured news items from the FactSet TruValue Labs database. Using a multinational framework including OECD nations, the study examines the dominant stock market indices in the selected countries. A key factor in choosing the FactSet TruValue Labs database is the inclusion of data from more than 267,000 companies that form the key global indexes. The database is constructed from the 26 categories established by the Sustainability Accounting

Standards Board (SASB) (FactSet, n.d.). To conclude, the study also includes numerous ESG dimensions to incorporate and analyze sustainability-related issues. With consideration of the news sources chosen in this study, “TruValue Spotlight Events-SASB” and “TruValue Spotlight-SASB (Limited History)” were selected.

The sample in this study includes 25 countries of the 38 OECD nations. The countries are as follows: “Australia,” “Austria,” “Belgium,” “Canada,” “Chile,” “Colombia,” “Denmark,” “Finland,” “France,” “Germany,” “Greece,” “Ireland,” “Israel,” “Italy,” “Japan,” “Mexico,” “Netherlands,” “New Zealand,” “Norway,” “Republic of Korea,” “Spain,” “Sweden,” “Turkey,” “UK,” “USA.” The other 13 countries, those under the influence of former Eastern Bloc or Soviets (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia), that attained freedom from the Soviet occupation and underwent similar economic growth; Switzerland, Iceland, and Luxembourg, where human development is high news coverage data after applying all screening criteria is scarce; Portugal, is a member of the European Union and has slightly less developed economy compared to the larger Western European economies; and, Costa Rica, was the most recent (2021) member of the OECD. These countries do have limited capitalization ratios, share turnover ratios, and trading volumes. There are a limited number of publicly traded companies in some countries, which limits their access to sufficient, significant, and moderate news.

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When selecting the countries in the study population, criteria related to market depth and representativeness are applied to ensure the statistical robustness of the data. Due to practical constraints regarding data availability, a purposive sampling strategy has been employed by the target population. The sample study consists of 591 publicly traded companies operating in the capital markets of the 25 OECD member countries listed above. In selecting these firms, the criterion used is that they must be listed on stock market indices comprising the 20–40 largest and most liquid companies in their respective countries. However, the United States, the United Kingdom, South Korea, Israel, Canada, and New Zealand are exceptions to this rule. Details regarding which stock market indices were included in the analysis are provided in Table 1.

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is used to calculate abnormal returns (AR), with the market return as one of its variables. The dataset comprises daily closing prices of various stock market indices from different nations, sourced from the FactSet database, for the two-year period from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023. The stock market indices are specifically chosen to encompass the 20-40 largest and most liquid firms in each country. The United States, the United Kingdom, South Korea, Israel, Canada, and New Zealand are exceptions to this rule, however. Table 1 explains the justification for selecting each index.

Table 1. Stock Exchange Indices

Country	Stock Exchange	Index	Description
USA	Nasdaq	Nasdaq 100	Covers the 100 largest and most liquid Nasdaq-listed companies and is preferred over the DJIA for its broader representation of technology and growth firms.
Germany	Frankfurt Stock Exchange	DAX	Includes the 40 largest and most liquid German companies, selected as the closest alternative to a top 20 index.
Australia	Australian Securities Exchange (ASX)	S&P/ASX 20	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid Australian companies.
Austria	Vienna Stock Exchange	ATX	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid companies in Austria.
Belgium	Euronext Brussels	BEL 20	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid companies in Belgium.
United Kingdom	London Stock Exchange	FTSE 100	Includes the 100 largest and most liquid UK companies, preferred over AIM indices for broader market representation.
Denmark	Copenhagen Stock Exchange	OMX C 20	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid Danish companies.
Finland	Helsinki Stock Exchange	OMX H 25	Covers the 25 largest and most liquid Finnish companies.
France	Euronext Paris	CAC 40	Includes the 40 largest and most liquid French companies, selected as the closest alternative to a top 20 index.
Republic of Korea	Korea Exchange	KOSPI 50	Covers the 50 largest and most liquid Korean companies, a broader index preferred to preserve news observations.
Netherlands	Euronext Amsterdam	AEX	Covers the 25 largest and most liquid Dutch companies.
Ireland	Euronext Dublin	ISEQ Overall	Broad market index including all listed Irish companies (26 firms).

Spain	Madrid Stock Exchange	IBEX 35	Covers the 35 largest and most liquid Spanish companies, selected as the closest alternative to a top 20 index.
Israel	Tel Aviv Stock Exchange	TA 125	Covers the 125 largest and most liquid Israeli companies; a broader index is preferred to maintain sample size.
Sweden	Stockholm Stock Exchange	OMX S 30	Covers the 30 largest and most liquid Swedish companies; a broader index is preferred to maintain the sample size.
Italy	Borsa Italiana (Milan Stock Exchange)	FTSE MIB	Includes the 40 largest and most liquid Italian companies, selected as the closest alternative to a top 20 index.
Japan	Tokyo Stock Exchange	TOPIX 20	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid Japanese companies.
Canada	Toronto Stock Exchange	S&P/TSX 60	Covers the 60 largest and most liquid Canadian companies, a broader index preferred to preserve news observations.
Colombia	Colombia Stock Exchange (BVC)	COLCAP	Covers the 20 largest and most liquid companies in Colombia.
Mexico	Mexican Stock Exchange (BMV)	S&P/BMV IPC	Covers the 35 largest and most liquid Mexican companies; a broader index is preferred to preserve new observations.
Norway	Oslo Stock Exchange	OBX	Covers the 25 largest and most liquid Norwegian companies.
Chile	Santiago Stock Exchange	S&P IPSA	Covers the 40 largest and most liquid Chilean companies, selected as the closest alternative to a top 20 index.
Turkey	Borsa Istanbul	BIST 30	Covers the 30 largest and most liquid Turkish companies.
New Zealand	New Zealand Stock Exchange	NZX 50	Covers the 50 largest and most liquid New Zealand companies; a broader index is preferred to preserve new observations.
Greece	Athens Stock Exchange	FTSE/ATHEX Large Cap	Covers the 25 largest and most liquid Greek companies.

The primary independent variable of this study comprises the daily closing prices of 591 firms (the full components of the relevant stock market indexes mentioned in the previous section) from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023. This type of data is also captured from the FactSet database.

For the risk-free interest rate, data on the 10-year government bond yields of the countries included in the analysis are compiled from the Bloomberg Terminal database. Within the framework of the CAPM, Sharpe (1964) defines the risk-free interest rate (pure rate of interest) as an investment instrument with a guaranteed return and no risk. Since the study is conducted on OECD countries, it is highly unlikely that these governments would face

difficulties in repaying their debts, and their government bonds align with Sharpe's definition. As 10-year bonds are among the most liquid securities in the market, the reliability of their market prices is high.

Although the risk-free interest rate used in the study is the 10-year government bond, since the analyses are conducted using daily events and daily stock and stock index returns, the data is obtained at a daily frequency using the Bloomberg Historical Data (BDH) function from the Bloomberg terminal. Bonds trade daily in secondary markets, and the Bloomberg database stores these daily yields (yield to maturity) as historical time series and provides them at a daily frequency.

The financial data in the dataset (stocks, stock market indices, and government bond prices) are extracted from end-of-day trading data. Although the study's time frame covers only weekdays, there may be days when a particular country's stock market is closed due to special occasions or other specific circumstances. Due to the conduct of a multinational study, official holidays may vary by nation, and data on such holidays may be missing. We fill in missing observations from each event using linear interpolation before beginning the analysis. Then, the price data is converted to a return series using a simple return calculation, as this approach is more suitable due to the CAPM's attributes. The returns are subjected to the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which tests for stationarity at the 5 percent significance level, a key assumption in time series analysis. Unit root tests indicate that the risk-free interest rate (RF) and market return (RM) series are stationary, while the stock return series are not ($p < 0.05$). Hence, the series that is not stationary is converted to stationary by calculating its first logarithmic differences. After calculating the log difference, all the data are deemed suitable for the regression model, allowing the CAPM Beta to be calculated using OLS.

All data modifications and the empirical analysis in this study are conducted in Python.

Our methodology closely aligns with both traditional and contemporary research approaches in event studies. The primary goal of an event study is to determine the short-run effects of particular information or events on the value of financial assets, leading the

literature to favor narrow event windows (MacKinlay, 1997; Brown & Warner, 1985). In our study, we chose the $[-1, +1]$ and $[-3, +3]$ event windows to minimize the information diffusion and dampen the effects of simultaneous macro and systemic shocks. That decision aligns with evidence that news about ESG and sustainability can significantly impact a company's stock prices. The market model and CAPM method for abnormal return estimation follow the traditional event study literature pattern to the greatest extent possible. MacKinlay (1997) emphasizes that the market model is one of the most widely used techniques, due to its computational simplicity and the likelihood that it will yield accurate forecasts under short events. This study uses stock market indices and risk-free interest rates for specific countries, given that market conditions differ across countries. Thus, a model used to estimate expected returns builds a framework consistent with the international event study literature. We analyze the stationarity of financial data using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and add logarithmic differencing for robustness and quantitative stability.

An issue often discussed in the event study literature is the extent of variation induced by events, as well as the inability to control for cross-sectional correlation. Specifically, if parallel ESG news is delivered to multiple enterprises simultaneously, correlations between abnormal returns can exist (Boehmer et al. 1991; Kolari and Pynnönen 2010). To address these concerns, our study uses small event windows and nonparametric test techniques. By not requiring the normality of the return's assumption, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test provides a more robust measurement of increased variance and variance, which could impact the overall distribution across event days. This approach follows the non-parametric test framework proposed by Corrado (1989). Detecting and removing outliers using the Interquartile Range (IQR) approach is a common method in financial data analysis, as it improves the confidence/reproducibility of the findings. In data containing relatively rare but catastrophic shocks, such as ESG events, extreme values may lead to misleading estimates based on the mean and variance. Accordingly, using the IQR in combination to screen CAR values is a method that follows the robustness control suggested in the literature. The methodology employed in this study is in contradiction with the prevailing perspective in the event study literature. It provides a framework that mirrors contemporary discourse and is relevant to the examination of ESG

and sustainability-related events. These conclusions are statistically and economically valid, contingent on the examination of short event windows, market-model-driven normal return estimates, nonparametric testing, and additional reliability controls within a comprehensive structure. The study establishes a robust methodological framework grounded in the classic event study literature and provides new empirical insights at the intersection of ESG and finance.

Abnormal returns denote the deviation of a company's stock return from its expected return, considering market fluctuations and other systemic risks. The market model is a conventional approach for calculating abnormal return. The model quantifies a stock's reactions to market returns via its beta (β) coefficient. The technique of our study is formulated utilizing the subsequent CAPM:

$$(1) R_i = R_F + \beta_i(R_M - R_F)$$

- R_i : Expected return (closing price of stock "i"),
- R_F : Risk-free interest rate (10-year sovereign bond),
- R_M : Market return (closing price of stock index).

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The β parameter in CAPM is computed using the following OLS regression model.

$$(2) R_i = \alpha_i + \beta_i(R_M) + \varepsilon_i$$

- α_i : Represents the return of a stock that is independent of market fluctuations,
- β_i : Represents the susceptibility of a stock to market fluctuations (systematic risk), and
- ε_i : Represents the error term that remains unaccounted for by the model.

Upon evaluating the market model coefficients (α and β), the abnormal return (AR) for each day "t" is computed using the subsequent formula:

$$(3) AR_{it} = R_{it} - (R_{Ft} + \beta_{it}(R_{Mt} - R_{Ft}))$$

The daily abnormal returns (AR_{it}) computed over the estimation period are aggregated to derive the cumulative abnormal return (CAR). This CAR value signifies the cumulative anomalous effect of the event during a designated timeframe. This event study utilizes two panels: Panel A and Panel B.

Panel A:

Estimation Window: Analyses closing prices from 255 days before the news publication date to the day prior to the news publication date [-255 -1].

$$CAR = \sum_{t=-255}^{t=-1} AR_{it}$$

Event Window: Analyses closing prices from 1 day before to 1 day after the news release date [-1 +1].

$$(4) CAR = \sum_{t=-1}^{t=1} AR_{it}$$

Panel B:

Estimation Window: Analyses closing prices from 255 days before the news publication date through the 3 days prior [-255 -3].

$$CAR = \sum_{t=-255}^{t=-3} AR_{it}$$

Event Window: Analyses closing prices from 3 days before to 3 days after the news release date [-3, +3].

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In financial data, particularly in event studies, excessive values or outliers can distort the analytical results. Such values may hinder the detection of genuinely unusual extreme occurrences. Recognizing and effectively managing outliers enhances the model's dependability and the results' generalizability. Therefore, the Interquartile Range (IQR) technique is utilized for all computed CAR values. The calculation utilizes the formula $IQR = Q3 - Q1$, with a lower limit of $Q1 - 1.5$ and an upper limit of $Q3 + 1.5$. All CAR values beyond these thresholds are deemed outliers and are omitted from the analysis.

We use the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test to determine whether measurements across two different time windows in the same sample differ significantly. Median discrepancies

between the estimated and actual CAR values are indicated in both panels. The test assesses the median difference between two dependent groups (pre-event and post-event) for ordinal data (firms). The results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test are shown in Table 2. Thus, the mean CAR of Panel A prediction window is -0.0228, and the median CAR is -0.0242; these are 0.0021 and 0.0007, respectively, for the event window. The differences between median values mean that the event is expected to have a positive bias in the CAR values. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test uses a p-value of 0.0000. A p-value of less than 0.05 (or 0.001) indicates a statistically significant difference between the estimation window and the event window CAR. This indicates that ESG news is returning statistically significant abnormal returns in the very short window. Values for mean CAR are -0.0075 in Panel B, and the median CAR is -0.0106; these data should be -0.0008 and -0.0014 for the event window, respectively. Although negative means and medians are shown at both points, they are closer to zero in the event window. It may signify a lower degree of the negative impact. The p-value is 0.1184, demonstrating that if the p-value exceeds 0.05, there is no statistically significant difference between the estimation window CAR values and the event window CAR values. This indicates that ESG news provides no statistically meaningful abnormal returns in the wider window.

Table 2. Results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

	Panel A		Panel B	
	Estimation Window [-255, -1]	Event Window [-1, +1]	Estimation Window [-255, -3]	Event Window [-3, +3]
Mean (CAR)	-0.0228	0.0021	-0.0075	-0.0008
Median (CAR)	-0.0242	0.0007	-0.0106	-0.0014
Std (CAR)	0.2979	0.0539	0.2957	0.0530
Wilcoxon Test Statistic	1,218,174		2,004,627	
P-value	0.0000 ($p < 0.05^*$)		0.1184 ($p > 0.05^*$)	

* The Wilcoxon signed-rank test investigates whether median CARs differ significantly from zero. In Panel A, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected at the 5percent significance level, while in Panel B, it cannot be rejected.

Figure 1 illustrates the boxplot and histogram generated for Panel A. Both plots demonstrate a substantial difference between the two distributions, suggesting that the event markedly reduces the variation in CAR values and centralizes them more closely around zero. This offers compelling preliminary evidence that events induce a

“normalization” and “focusing” effect on market reactions.

Figure 1. Boxplot and Histogram for Panel A

5.2. Sentiment Analysis

The study’s sub-hypothesis in the second part analyzes the positive or negative influence of news about the event window on stock returns. Materiality metric defined before by computing the absolute difference between all CAR 2 (CAR values in the event window) and CAR 1 (CAR values in the estimation window) values obtained in Panel A of the previous section. The absolute difference is applied here only with the amount of the change in CAR, not the direction, enabling us to measure the distance between two CAR values.

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$$(6) \text{ CAR Differences} = |\text{CAR 2} - \text{CAR 1}|$$

Figure 2 presents a box plot depicting the distribution of the absolute difference ($|\text{CAR 2} - \text{CAR 1}|$) for both positive and negative sentiments.

Figure 2. Distribution of Absolute Deviations As per the News Direction

In Figure 2, the line in the box indicates the median; the height of the box shows the interquartile range (the middle 50% of the dataset); and the whiskers show the minimum and maximum values. The plot shows that the median is approximately 0.18-0.20 for negative sentiment and 0.15-0.17 for positive sentiment. Most absolute difference values for negative sentiment fall within the range 0.10-0.35, as indicated by the IQR. For positive sentiment, most absolute difference values are clustered between 0.08 and 0.33. The interquartile range (IQR) is narrower for negative sentiment—values range from around 0.05 to 0.75. For positive sentiment, the average absolute difference is between 0.05 and 0.70. While median values suggest no statistically significant difference between groups, hypothesis testing is required to confirm it. Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, we investigate whether our novel CAR Dif. variation has a difference between Positive and Negative Sentiment. This test is chosen because it does not assume normality (i.e., it is nonparametric). The Kruskal-Wallis test looks for a statistically significant difference in the medians of the absolute difference variables for positive and negative news.

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Kruskal-Wallis Test (Absolute CAR Differences): $H = 0.7415$, $p = 0.3892$.

A p-value greater than 0.05 indicates that the null H_0 is not rejected. The CAR values, which vary with news, do not differ greatly between positive and negative news. These observations are consistent with the Efficient Market Hypothesis. Thus, markets immediately integrate knowledge into prices. Positive and negative news bring new

information into the market. The direction of change (upward vs. downward) can be pronounced, though the overall magnitude can be equally variable, depending on how significant the evidence is for incorporating the information and whether it is priced in by the news, depending on the information's importance. In particular, when an unexpected event occurs in the market, the reaction to the news can be significant, regardless of how surprising the news is. In behavioral finance theory, Loss Aversion holds that the likelihood of an individual reacting differently to a loss is greater than to a gain. However, this usually relates to “perceived value” or “utility.” The magnitude of the price movement is immense, and the potential for profit (positive) and risk (negative) is so large that investors are forced to take similar positions in absolute value.

The paper examines ESG news and its association with abnormal short-term stock outcomes, capital market investors, and their behavior. The empirical results show that ESG news brings relatively significant short-term effects on stock prices in tight event windows. The short event window [-1, +1] results show a statistically significant change in their cumulative abnormal returns compared to the estimation window, indicating that investors can quickly fill the time in stocks with ESG information. This matches the semi-strong form of the Efficient Market Hypothesis, which states that common information is quickly incorporated into market prices. However, when it is applied to [-3, +3], the statistical significance of abnormal returns decreases, suggesting that the market response to ESG news is only temporary. We also find that the information shock dissipates quickly and that a persistent mispricing effect is not generated, so we eliminate abnormal returns for much of the time. This account fits behavioral finance, such as the attention framework or the overreaction theory. These assumptions suggest that investors respond strongly to major news initially, though these responses eventually settle down. The market's response to positive and negative ESG news shows no statistically significant difference in the magnitude of CAR. There are small differences in the medians in the descriptive statistics. Nevertheless, the Kruskal-Wallis test shows that the absolute difference in CAR is not significant between news sentiment. Hypothesis H1b is therefore not corroborated. The finding is similar to that in EPH, indicating that investors can also evaluate sustainability-related information judiciously. The findings show that ESG has

short-term economic importance in capital markets. By focusing on news-driven, real-time ESG signals rather than static ESG ratings, we can provide a more dynamic view of how sustainability-related signals are handled and valued today. In this paper, we address how ESG-related information is processed and valued more dynamically. The findings suggest that investors pay close attention to ESG changes in practice and adjust their assessments of a company's risks and future cash flow. The findings have major implications for corporate bosses, investors, and regulators.

ESG news is an important source for investors because it can have a significant impact on portfolio returns, especially in low-trading-activity environments. The results suggest that regulatory authorities and standards-setting entities are integrating sustainability-related information into financial decision-making. The findings demonstrate that ESG news is associated with quantifiable, statistically significant short-term abnormal returns. However, the benefits decline over extended periods. The results confirm the view that sustainability information has become an essential part of financial markets and that ESG changes are currently actively considered when determining asset prices.

Hakem Değerlendirmesi: Dış Bağımsız- Çift Kör Hakemlik

Yazar Katkısı: Merve Bilen Demirkol %100

Destek ve Teşekkür Beyanı: Çalışma için destek alınmamıştır.

Etik Onay: Bu çalışma etik onay gerektiren herhangi bir insan veya hayvan araştırması içermemektedir.

Çıkar Çatışması Beyanı: Çalışma ile ilgili herhangi bir kurum veya kişi ile çıkar çatışması bulunmamaktadır.

Peer Review: Independent double-blind

Author Contributions: Merve Bilen Demirkol 100%

Funding and Acknowledgement: No support was received for the study.

Ethics Approval: This study does not contain any human or animal research that requires ethical approval.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest with any institution or person related to the study.

Albuquerque, R., Koskinen, Y. & Zhang, C. (2019). Corporate social responsibility and firm risk: Theory and empirical evidence. *Management Science*, 65(10), 4451–4469. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2018.3043>

- Albuquerque, R., Koskinen, Y., Yang, S. & Zhang, C. (2020). Resiliency of environmental and social stocks: Evidence from the COVID-19 crisis. *Review of Corporate Finance Studies*, 9(3), 593–621. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rcfs/cfaa011>
- Aouadi, A. & Marsat, S. (2018). Do ESG controversies matter for firm value? Evidence from international data. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 151(4), 1027–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3213-8>
- Bansal, P. (2005). Evolving sustainably: A longitudinal study of corporate sustainable development. *Strategic Management Journal*, 26(3), 197–218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.441>
- Barberis, N., Shleifer, A. & Vishny, R. (1998). A model of investor sentiment. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 49(3), 307–343.
- Becchetti, L., Ciciretti, R., Hasan, I. & Kobeissi, N. (2012). Corporate social responsibility and shareholders' value. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(11), 1628–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.10.022>
- Boehmer, E., Musumeci, J. & Poulsen, A. B. (1991). Event-study methodology under conditions of event-induced variance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 30(2), 253–272.
- Bolton, P. & Kacperczyk, M. (2021). Do investors care about carbon risk? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 142(2), 517–549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2021.05.008>
- Brown, S. J. & Warner, J. B. (1985). Using daily stock returns: The case of event studies. *Journal of Financial Economics* 14(1):3–31.
- Corrado, C. J. (1989). A nonparametric test for abnormal security-price performance in event studies. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 23(2), 385–395.
- De Bondt W. F. M. & Thaler, R. (1985). Does the stock market overreact? *Journal of Finance*, 40(3), 793–805.
- Donaldson, T. & Preston, L. E. (1995). The stakeholder theory of the corporation: Concepts, evidence, and implications. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 65–91. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258887>

- Dorfleitner, G. & Zhang, R. (2024). ESG news and stock market reaction: A global analysis with a fine-tuned BERT model. *Schmalenbach Journal of Business Research*, 76(2), 197–244. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41471-024-00182-3>
- El Ghouli, S., Guedhami, O., Kwok, C. C. Y. & Mishra, D. R. (2011). Does corporate social responsibility affect the cost of capital? *Journal of Banking & Finance* 35(9):2388–2406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2011.02.007>
- Elkington, J. (2004). *Enter the triple bottom line*. In: Henriques A, Richardson J (eds) *The triple bottom line: Does it all add up?* Earthscan, pp. 1–16.
- FactSet (n.d.). *FactSet Truvalue scores & spotlights*. <https://www.factset.com/marketplace/catalog/product/factset-truvalue-scores-and-spotlights>
- Fama, E. F. (1970). Efficient capital markets: A review of theory and empirical work. *Journal of Finance*, 25(2), 383–417.
- Fama E. F., Fisher, L., Jensen, M. C. & Roll, R. (1969). The adjustment of stock prices to new information. *International Economic Review*, 10(1), 1–21.
- Friede, G., Busch, T. & Bassen, A. (2015). ESG and financial performance: Aggregated evidence from more than 2000 empirical studies. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 5(4), 210–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2015.1118917>
- Friedman, M. (1970). *The social responsibility of business is to increase its profits*. New York Times, 13 September 1970. <https://www.nytimes.com/1970/09/13/archives/a-friedman-doctrine-the-social-responsibility-of-business-is-to.html>
- Goss, A. & Roberts, G. S. (2011). The impact of corporate social responsibility on the cost of bank loans. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 35(7), 1794–1810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2010.12.002>
- Hong, H., Kubik, J. D. & Scheinkman, J. A. (2012). *Financial constraints on corporate goodness*. NBER Working Paper No 18476. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w18476>
- Kolari, J. W. & Pynnönen, S. (2010) Event study testing with cross-sectional correlation of abnormal returns. *Review of Financial Studies*, 23(11), 3996–4025. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhq072>

- Krueger, P., Sautner, Z. & Starks, L. T. (2020). The importance of climate risks for institutional investors. *Review of Financial Studies*, 33(3), 1067–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhz137>
- Lee, S. Y., Park, Y. S. & Klassen, R. D. (2015) Market responses to firms' voluntary carbon disclosure: Evidence from the carbon disclosure project. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 22(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1321>
- Li, Q., Watts, E. M. & Zhu, C. (2024). Retail investors and ESG news. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 78(1), 101719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2024.101719>
- Lins, K. V., Servaes, H. & Tamayo, A. (2017). Social capital, trust, and firm performance: The value of corporate social responsibility during the financial crisis. *Journal of Finance*, 72(4), 1785–1824. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jofi.12505>
- MacKinlay A. C. (1997). Event studies in economics and finance. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 35(1), 13–39.
- Pankratz, N., Bauer, R., Derwall, J. (2023). Climate change, firm performance, and investor surprises. *Management Science*, 69(12), 7352–7398. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2023.4685>
- Patell, J. M. (1976). Corporate forecasts of earnings per share and stock price behavior: Empirical tests. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 14(2), 246–276.
- Preston, L. E. & O'Bannon, D. P. (1997). The corporate social-financial performance relationship: A typology and analysis. *Business & Society*, 36(4), 419–429.
- Serafeim, G. & Yoon, A. (2022). Which corporate ESG news does the market react to? *Financial Analysts Journal*, 78(1), 59–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0015198X.2021.1973879>
- Servaes, H. & Tamayo, A. (2013). The impact of corporate social responsibility on firm value: The role of customer awareness. *Management Science*, 59(5), 1045–1061. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1120.1630>
- Sharpe, W. F. (1964). Capital asset prices: A theory of market equilibrium under conditions of risk. *Journal of Finance*, 19(3), 425–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1964.tb02865.x>

- Shiller, R. J. (1981). Do stock prices move too much to be justified by subsequent changes in dividends?. *American Economic Review*, 71(3), 421–436.
- Vu, T. N., Junttila, J. P. & Lehkonen, H. (2024). ESG news and long-run stock returns. *Finance Research Letters*, 60, 104915. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2023.104915>
- Waddock, S. A. & Graves, S. B. (1997). The corporate social performance–financial performance link. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(4), 303–319.